

BIM Washing as a Decoupling Mechanism: Analysis of Ceremonial Isomorphism in the Construction Industry

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Abstract

This article analyzes the phenomenon of BIM washing through the prism of institutional theory, presenting it as strategic decoupling driven by organizational isomorphism. While most studies on BIM (Building Information Modeling) assume rationality in technological choice, this analysis shows that organizations in the construction sector sometimes adopt BIM only symbolically, not because of operational benefits, but in response to institutional pressures (tender requirements, industry standards, or imitation of competitors). This leads to permanent decoupling, where the ceremonial facade of BIM advancement (certificates, positions, project portfolios, etc.) coexists with unchanged traditional design practices. Thus, BIM washing is not an accidental failure of implementation, but a rational strategy for managing the conflicting expectations of the institutional environment. The article extends institutional theory with a new concept of washing and offers practical implications for public policy and technology management in the construction industry.

Keywords: BIM washing, decoupling, institutional isomorphism, technology adoption, construction industry

Introduction

BIM (Building Information Modeling) has been widely adopted as the dominant tool in the digitization of the construction industry (Borkowski, 2024). Digitization, understood as the process of introducing digital technologies into the construction environment, has the potential to support the production of higher quality goods and services at reduced costs (Baryłka et al., 2025). Industry reports indicate that nearly 80% of design companies declare that they use BIM (Dodge Data & Analytics, 2023; NBS, 2020), and the governments of many countries have introduced mandatory BIM requirements for public projects (UK Government Construction Strategy, 2011, EC Handbook, 2016). However, despite this seemingly widespread adoption, the construction industry continues to have the lowest productivity of any sector of the economy (McKinsey, 2020), with high rates of design errors, budget overruns, and construction delays (Abdelalim et al., 2025). This paradox, i.e., the widespread declared adoption of BIM without any visible transformation of the industry, requires a theoretical explanation that goes beyond the models of technology acceptance that dominate the literature (e.g., Technology Acceptance Model or Diffusion of Innovations). Current research points to a rather linear process of BIM implementation, ignoring the complex institutional and political context in which organizations, mainly companies, operate. This article proposes an alternative concept, rooted in institutional theory (Meyer & Rowan, 1977; DiMaggio & Powell, 1983). For at least a decade, there has been a noticeable trend of so-called BIM washing, i.e., the deliberate creation of a false image of BIM advancement while maintaining traditional practices. This is not only an ethical problem or a competence deficit, but also a strategic decoupling, i.e., a rational response by organizations to conflicting environmental pressures.

Thus, the main research questions are: Why do organizations in the construction sector adopt BIM symbolically rather than genuinely? How does BIM washing become a rational institutional strategy?

By integrating three key theoretical concepts organizational isomorphism (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983), decoupling (Meyer & Rowan, 1977), and the titular BIM washing as a legitimization

46 strategy a new framework for understanding this dysfunction of BIM technology
47 implementations in an institutional context is presented. The article contributes to the current
48 state of knowledge and technology in the following ways:

- 49 • It presents the phenomenon of BIM washing as strategic decoupling, going beyond
50 moralizing interpretations of fraud or dishonesty.
- 51 • It explains the theoretical mechanism through which institutional isomorphism leads to
52 permanent decoupling.
- 53 • It extends institutional theory to include BIM washing as a general phenomenon in
54 technology adoption.
- 55 • It points to practical implications for public policy, highlighting the inappropriateness
56 of certification requirements without verification mechanisms.

57 **Methodology**

58 **Research design and philosophical approach**

59 This study adopts an interpretive research paradigm grounded in institutional theory to examine
60 the phenomenon of BIM washing as a form of strategic decoupling in the construction industry.
61 The interpretivist approach is particularly suitable for investigating how organizational actors
62 construct meaning around technology adoption and legitimacy, as well as how institutional
63 pressures shape organizational responses (Skarbek, 2020). Unlike positivist approaches that
64 assume objective reality, interpretivism acknowledges that organizational phenomena such as
65 ceremonial adoption are socially constructed and require understanding from the perspective
66 of actors within the institutional context (Berger & Luckmann, 2023).

67 The research design integrates conceptual theory-building with systematic qualitative analysis.
68 This approach aligns with the methodological tradition in neo-institutional research, which
69 emphasizes the development of theoretical frameworks capable of explaining macro-level
70 patterns of organizational behavior (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983; Greenwood et al., 2017). The
71 theoretical nature of this study responds to calls for more sophisticated conceptual development
72 in BIM research, which has been criticized for its predominantly technocentric orientation
73 (Papadonikolaki, 2018; Dainty et al., 2017).

74 **Theoretical framework development**

75 The theoretical framework was developed through an iterative process involving three distinct
76 phases, following the guidelines for theory-building research proposed by Eisenhardt and
77 Graebner (2007) and elaborated for institutional studies.

78 79 **Phase 1: Literature synthesis and gap identification**

80 The first phase involved a comprehensive review of three intersecting bodies of literature: (a)
81 BIM adoption and implementation research, (b) neo-institutional theory focusing on
82 decoupling and isomorphism, and (c) organizational legitimacy and ceremonial adoption
83 studies across various domains (including greenwashing, CSR washing, and digital
84 transformation washing).

85 Literature searches were conducted across Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar
86 databases using combinations of keywords including "BIM adoption," "BIM implementation
87 barriers," "institutional isomorphism," "decoupling," "ceremonial adoption," "legitimacy,"
88 "greenwashing," and "technology washing." Articles were screened based on relevance to the
89 intersection of technology adoption and institutional pressures. This phase identified a critical
90 gap: while BIM adoption literature focuses on technical and organizational barriers (Chan et

91 al., 2019; Babatunde et al., 2021), it largely ignores the institutional mechanisms that may
92 encourage symbolic rather than substantive adoption.

93

94 **Phase 2: Conceptual integration**

95 The second phase involved the conceptual integration of institutional theory constructs
96 (isomorphism, decoupling, legitimacy) with observations from BIM practice and industry
97 reports. Drawing on Whetten's (1989) criteria for theoretical contribution, the framework was
98 developed by: (a) identifying the key constructs (coercive, mimetic, and normative
99 isomorphism; policy-practice decoupling; ceremonial vs. substantive adoption), (b) specifying
100 relationships among constructs, (c) defining boundary conditions specific to the construction
101 industry context, and (d) articulating the underlying logic connecting pressures, responses, and
102 outcomes.

103 This integration draws on Bromley and Powell's (2012) reconceptualization of decoupling as a
104 contemporary phenomenon that extends beyond Meyer and Rowan's (1977) original
105 formulation. Specifically, the framework incorporates the distinction between policy-practice
106 decoupling (where formal policies are adopted but not implemented) and means-ends
107 decoupling (where policies are implemented but fail to achieve intended outcomes),
108 recognizing that BIM washing may manifest in both forms.

109

110 **Phase 3: Framework validation and refinement**

111 The theoretical framework was refined through engagement with industry evidence and
112 secondary sources, including government mandates and policy documents (UK Government
113 Construction Strategy, 2011; EU BIM Handbook, 2016), industry reports (NBS National BIM
114 Reports 2015-2024; Dodge Data & Analytics Smart Market Reports), professional body
115 publications (buildingSMART International standards documentation), and case examples
116 from industry publications and trade press.

117 This triangulation of theoretical concepts with industry evidence follows the abductive
118 reasoning approach recommended for institutional research, allowing iterative movement
119 between theory and observation to enhance the plausibility and explanatory power of the
120 proposed framework.

121 **Analytical approach**

122 The study employs conceptual analysis as its primary analytical method, following the
123 approach outlined by Jabareen (2009) for building conceptual frameworks. This method
124 involves: (a) mapping the sources of data (theoretical and empirical literature), (b) extensive
125 reading and categorizing of the selected data, (c) identifying and naming concepts, (d)
126 deconstructing and categorizing the concepts, (e) integrating concepts into a coherent
127 framework, (f) synthesizing and resynthesizing as needed, and (g) validating the conceptual
128 framework. The analysis specifically focused on identifying mechanisms through which
129 institutional pressures translate into organizational responses, conditions under which
130 decoupling becomes a rational strategy, artifacts and signals that constitute the "front stage" of
131 BIM washing, and feedback loops that perpetuate the phenomenon at field level.

132 The cyclical model of BIM washing (presented in Section 4) was developed using process
133 theory methodology (Langley, 1999). Process models explain phenomena through sequences
134 of events and activities rather than variance-based correlations between variables. This
135 approach is particularly appropriate for understanding how institutional pressures unfold over
136 time and how organizational responses become institutionalized at the field level.

137 The four-phase model (Institutional Pressures – Strategic Dilemma – Decoupling Strategy –
138 Perpetuation) was constructed by: identifying key events and decision points from the

139 literature, establishing temporal ordering of these events, specifying the mechanisms linking
140 phases, and incorporating feedback dynamics that explain persistence.

141 **Quality and rigor**

142 Following Corley and Gioia's (2011) framework for assessing theoretical contributions, this
143 study addresses both the "utility" and "originality" dimensions of theoretical knowledge: Utility
144 is demonstrated through: (a) practical implications for policy-makers and practitioners,
145 (b) explanation of a paradox (widespread BIM adoption alongside unchanged industry
146 performance), and (c) provision of an actionable framework for diagnosis and intervention.
147 Originality is established through: (a) introducing the concept of BIM washing to the academic
148 literature, (b) applying institutional theory to a new empirical domain (construction technology
149 adoption), and (c) extending decoupling theory by specifying mechanisms particular to
150 technology adoption contexts.

151 **Limitations of the methodology**

152 Several limitations of this methodological approach should be acknowledged. First, as a
153 conceptual study, the framework has not been tested empirically. While grounded in
154 established theory and supported by secondary evidence, direct empirical validation through
155 case studies, surveys, or ethnographic research would strengthen the claims made. Second, the
156 study draws primarily on English-language sources and may not fully capture institutional
157 dynamics in non-Western construction markets. Third, the framework assumes a degree of
158 intentionality in organizational responses that may overstate the strategic rationality of actors;
159 in practice, decoupling may emerge from unintended consequences and organizational inertia
160 as much as from deliberate strategy.
161 These limitations point to important directions for future empirical research, discussed in the
162 concluding section.

163 **Literature review**

164 **Research on BIM adoption and criticism of technocentrism**

165 The dominant paradigm in BIM implementation research is based on technology acceptance
166 models derived from TAM (Technology Acceptance Model) (Davis, 1989) and DoI (Diffusion
167 of Innovations) (Rogers, 1962). These approaches assume the rationality of organizational
168 actors and a linear process of technology adoption through the following phases: awareness,
169 interest, evaluation, trial, and adoption (Succar et al., 2012; Eastman et al., 2011). BIM maturity
170 models generally show implementation as a gradual progression through defined levels (Level
171 0 to Level 3), where organizations systematically develop technical, process, and
172 organizational competencies (Succar et al., 2012). However, this type of literature focuses on
173 identifying technological barriers, from a lack of seamless interoperability and significant
174 software purchase costs to deficits in standards, knowledge, and training, as the main obstacles
175 to BIM adoption (Arayici et al., 2011; Eastman et al., 2011; Chan, Olawumi, & Ho, 2019;
176 Babatunde, Udejaja, & Adekunle, 2021). However, these approaches have fundamental
177 limitations. First, they assume that adoption is a binary category or continuum, ignoring the
178 possibility of so-called symbolic (or ceremonial) adoption, where an organization declares its
179 use of technology without actually changing its existing practices. Second, they treat the
180 institutional context as an external moderating variable rather than a fundamental element of
181 the adoption process. Third, they do not explain the paradox described earlier, i.e., why, despite
182 the removal of technical barriers (greater software availability, widespread training, multiple
183 standards), real digital transformation is not taking place.

184 **Institutional theory in organizational studies**

185 Neo-institutionalism in organizational theory (Meyer & Rowan, 1977; DiMaggio & Powell,
186 1983) offers an alternative perspective in which organizations strive not only for technical
187 efficiency, but above all for institutional legitimacy. Legitimacy is the social acceptance of an
188 organization as normal, appropriate, or professional. It is now becoming a critical resource for
189 survival, regardless of actual operational efficiency. Meyer and Rowan (1977) in their classic
190 work 'Institutionalized Organizations: Formal Structure as Myth and Ceremony' argue that the
191 formal structure of an organization often serves ceremonial purposes, i.e., signaling compliance
192 with the expectations of the environment, rather than actual technical goals. Organizations
193 adopt structures and practices considered rational or modern not because they increase
194 efficiency and improve performance, but because conformity to rationalized institutional myths
195 provides legitimacy. The key mechanism for the spread of these rationalized myths is
196 institutional isomorphism, i.e., the process by which organizations in the same organizational
197 field become increasingly similar to each other (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983). Researchers
198 identify three types of isomorphism: coercive (induced by regulations and legal requirements),
199 normative (professionalization and industry standards), and mimetic (imitation in conditions
200 of uncertainty).

201 **Decoupling as a strategic response by companies**

202 When organizations face conflicting expectations from their institutional environment, such as
203 the requirement for innovation while simultaneously needing stability, the most common
204 response is decoupling, i.e., the structural separation of the formal structure from actual
205 operational practices (Meyer & Rowan, 1977).

206 Decoupling allows an organization to simultaneously:

- 207 • Gain legitimacy by demonstrating conformity to institutional expectations (*front stage*).
- 208 • Maintain operational stability and key competencies by continuing proven practices
209 (*back stage*).

210 In a comprehensive review of the literature, Bromley and Powell (2012) point out that
211 decoupling is not a marginal or dysfunctional phenomenon, but a fundamental feature of
212 contemporary organizations operating in complex institutional environments.

213 **Theoretical framework**

214 **Isomorphism as a pressure mechanism**

215 DiMaggio and Powell (1983) point out that the convergence of organizations within the same
216 organizational field is not solely the result of better practices or objective technological
217 advantages, but a consequence of institutional pressures that reward conformity to recognized
218 patterns of rationality. In the context of BIM, this means that organizations may declare their
219 adoption of information modeling not because it solves their operational problems, but because
220 BIM is becoming a social marker of modernity, professionalism, and correctness of operation.
221 Isomorphism acts here as a pressure-generating mechanism: it reduces uncertainty, organizes
222 stakeholder expectations, and at the same time creates conditions in which symbolic
223 compliance begins to have greater value than operational compliance.

224 The first source of pressure is coercive isomorphism, resulting from formal and informal
225 requirements imposed on organizations by actors with power over resources, the market, or
226 access to projects. In the area of BIM, coercion takes the form of government mandates and
227 public institution requirements that make participation in public procurement conditional on

228 BIM capability. An example is the UK Government Construction Strategy (2011), which
229 established a requirement to use Level 2 BIM in public projects (with implementation from
230 2016), as well as the spread of standards and certification regimes in which knowledge of the
231 multi-part ISO 19650 standard is sometimes treated as a condition for entry into large projects.
232 As a result, organizations may be de facto forced to declare BIM competence in order to
233 maintain access to the public procurement market, regardless of whether they have the real
234 capacity to use it in their daily design practices. This type of pressure rewards quick signals of
235 compliance (e.g., a souped-up image of BIM on the organization's website) rather than a deep
236 process transformation.

237 The second mechanism is mimetic isomorphism, which is particularly strong in conditions of
238 technological and strategic uncertainty. When organizations are unsure what the market will
239 look like in a few years, what standards will prevail, and what competencies will prove crucial,
240 they reduce uncertainty by imitating those entities that are considered leaders or models of
241 legitimacy. In BIM, this manifests itself in arguments such as: "if ARUP, Buro Happold, or
242 Foster+Partners are doing BIM, we have to as well," and in the belief that "it's better to have
243 BIM just in case," even if the organization's current practice remains rooted in traditional
244 procedures. Imitation often concerns not so much the deep manufacturing processes as their
245 visible symbols of success: creating positions such as BIM Manager, establishing BIM
246 departments, obtaining certificates, and promoting the use of BIM as a communication shortcut
247 telling the environment: we are modern and market-compatible. Mimicry thus leads to the
248 spread of solutions not because they are a proven technical quantum, but because they
249 constitute a socially recognizable spectrum of activities that reduce reputational risk.

250 The third source of pressure is normative isomorphism, rooted in professionalization: in the
251 processes of education, standardization, and institutional definition of how one should work in
252 a given profession. In the area of BIM, normative pressure is reinforced by study programs and
253 professional training promoting BIM as a modern technology, where new professions are
254 emerging (Borkowski, Mielnicki 2025), by industry associations and organizations (e.g.,
255 buildingSMART initiatives and standards), as well as by consultants and researchers who act
256 as BIM specialists, defining BIM as a marker of professionalism, maturity, and the ethos of
257 modern design. Such normative expectations create a strong identity imperative: an
258 organization that does not communicate its use of BIM may be considered outdated, unreliable,
259 or incapable of participating in the new industry order, even if its technical performance
260 remains competitive.

261 The combined effect of the three mechanisms of isomorphism is an intensification of pressure
262 to conform, but primarily of an institutional rather than a purely technical nature. Organizations
263 in the BIM field are encouraged (or forced) to adopt what is considered a rational myth of
264 modernity, as this brings legitimacy in the eyes of public and private clients, regulators,
265 partners, and professional circles. At the same time, isomorphism does not guarantee that the
266 practices adopted will be deeply integrated into operations; on the contrary, it may create
267 conditions conducive to separating the facade of compliance from real actions if the
268 environment rewards signals rather than verifiable results. In this sense, isomorphism is a key
269 pressure mechanism that paves the way for further phenomena of decoupling and strategic
270 ceremonial adoption, developed in subsequent parts of the theoretical framework.

271 **BIM washing as strategic decoupling**

272 In this theoretical framework, BIM washing is not treated as an implementation error or
273 temporary digital immaturity of an organization, but as a special case of decoupling: the
274 structural separation of formal declarations and artifacts visible to the environment from actual
275 operational practices. Decoupling is a classic response to the conflicting expectations of the

276 institutional environment, in which organizations must simultaneously demonstrate modernity
277 and compliance with prevailing norms, while maintaining production stability, predictability
278 of implementation, and protection of existing competencies. In the context of BIM, this
279 contradiction takes on a particularly pronounced form, as the environment (regulators, labor
280 market) expects the use of BIM as a condition of legitimacy, while real digital transformation
281 requires time, costs, reorganization, and the assumption of certain operational risks. In such a
282 configuration, there are grounds for a strategy in which an organization chooses symbolic
283 compliance instead of (or alongside) practical compliance. Thus, the following conceptual
284 definition is proposed: *BIM washing is the strategic production of symbolic evidence of BIM*
285 *advancement (e.g., certificates, portfolios, positions, marketing discourse) while maintaining*
286 *traditional design practices, carried out to obtain institutional legitimacy without incurring the*
287 *costs of actual digital transformation.*

288 This definition emphasizes that the subject of analysis is not the mere presence of BIM tools
289 in an organization, but the relationship between the "front stage" (what the organization shows
290 to the outside world as proof of modernity) and the "back stage" (how it coordinates work,
291 makes decisions, and produces documentation). BIM washing is therefore a mechanism of
292 legitimization: it enables institutional expectations to be met through artifacts that are easily
293 observable and difficult to verify in depth, without disrupting the stable operational core. The
294 key feature of this conceptualization is intentionality. BIM washing is not an accidental
295 misunderstanding or solely the result of low competence, but a conscious impression
296 management strategy in which the organization designs signals of compliance with the
297 dominant myth of rationality (colloquially, a professional company does BIM).

298 The second feature is selectivity, as investments are directed towards those elements that are
299 most visible to the institutional environment and work best as evidence of adoption (e.g., job
300 titles with the addition of BIM, BIM competency certificates, BIM-related offer wording,
301 demonstration 3D models), while practices requiring changes in procedures, responsibilities,
302 information flows, and work culture may remain unchanged.

303 The third feature is permanence. Washing does not have to be a transitional stage on the road
304 to BIM maturity but can stabilize as a permanent equilibrium because it provides legitimization
305 benefits at relatively low cost and with limited risk of destabilization.

306 Finally, the fourth feature is rationality, as it means that in the face of conflicting institutional
307 pressures, BIM washing can be a logical choice that maximizes legitimacy while minimizing
308 costs: the organization, in a sense, buys the acceptance of its environment with artifacts, rather
309 than paying the full price of process transformation.

310 Understood in this way, BIM washing is not only a normative label, but also an analytical tool
311 for describing a mechanism in which organizations maintain two parallel orders: a ceremonial
312 order, focused on compliance and reputation, and an operational order, focused on stability,
313 pace of work, and risk minimization. In the next part of the article, this mechanism is developed
314 as a self-perpetuating cycle in which isomorphic pressures and limited verifiability of practices
315 reinforce the profitability of symbolic adoption, thereby perpetuating decoupling as the
316 dominant pattern of enterprise functioning.

317 **Theoretical model: The BIM washing cycle**

318 Integrating isomorphism, decoupling, and washing, the following theoretical model of the BIM
319 washing perpetuation mechanism has been proposed, which goes through four key phases
320 forming a self-perpetuating cycle (Fig. 1).

321
322

Figure 1. The BIM washing cycle as a mechanism of decoupling (own elaboration).

323 The process of institutionalizing the ceremonial adoption of BIM technology in construction
324 organizations can be described as a sequence of four interrelated phases, the understanding of
325 which allows us to explain the mechanisms of the emergence and perpetuation of the
326 phenomenon referred to in the literature as BIM washing.

327 In the first phase, the organization experiences simultaneous isomorphic pressures from three
328 separate sources. Coercive pressures manifest themselves through formal regulatory
329 requirements, such as the multi-part ISO19650 standard or government mandates conditioning
330 participation in public tenders on the possession of specific competencies in building
331 information modeling. At the same time, mimetic pressures arise from observing competitors
332 who have created BIM Manager positions and established departments responsible for BIM
333 implementation. The third source is normative pressures, shaped by industry associations,
334 educational institutions, and researchers who define the professionalism of an organization
335 through the prism of BIM methodology.

336 In phase two, the organization faces a fundamental strategic dilemma that can be reduced to a
337 choice between two options. The first option involves a genuine digital transformation, which
338 entails high costs including investments in technological infrastructure, comprehensive training
339 programs, and a profound reorganization of operational processes. This transformation requires
340 a time horizon of at least three to five years and carries significant risks, including
341 destabilization of current operations, potential staff turnover, and uncertain return on
342 investment. An alternative is ceremonial adoption, known as BIM washing, which is
343 characterized by low costs limited to obtaining a few, often insignificant, certificates, creating
344 a BIM Manager position, which is in fact a Project Manager position, and purchasing software
345 licenses, which are not always BIM software, but often CAD3D. This option provides
346 immediate legitimization with minimal risk, as the basic activities and processes of the
347 organization remain unchanged.

348 The third phase involves a rational choice of a decoupling strategy, in which the organization
349 opts for the ceremonial option and creates a dual operating structure. At the facade level,
350 presented to the external environment, the organization displays the position of BIM Manager,
351 which is often held by a young employee with no real decision-making power, and acquired
352 certificates, e.g., ISO19650 compliance or individual employee certifications. The project

353 portfolio contains so-called BIM projects, which are in fact models created post factum for
354 marketing documentation purposes, and external communication is saturated with specialist
355 jargon referring to collaborative workflows or high-profile federated models. At the same time,
356 at the level of actual operations, invisible to external stakeholders, project coordination takes
357 place through traditional channels such as email, phone calls, and the exchange of drawings in
358 DWG or PDF format. The basic project documentation consists of drawings made using CAD
359 technology, decisions are made within traditional hierarchies during face-to-face meetings
360 without the use of CDE (Common Data Environment) environments, and the organizational
361 culture remains rooted in the belief that the existing working methods are good and therefore
362 sufficient.

363 In phase four, the cycle is perpetuated, with BIM washing becoming a self-reinforcing
364 phenomenon through the action of several interdependent mechanisms. Mimetic isomorphism
365 causes other organizations to observe the apparent success of companies using the ceremonial
366 adoption strategy, understood as gaining market legitimacy without incurring high
367 transformation costs, and to copy this strategy. This leads to the normalization of the
368 phenomenon, which over time becomes an informal industry standard, justified by the belief
369 that everyone is doing it. This mechanism is further reinforced by the lack of effective
370 verification, as formal audits conducted as part of certification focus on document control
371 rather than actual operational practices. Finally, the asymmetry of knowledge between
372 contractors and clients means that customers do not have the expertise to distinguish between
373 a ceremonial facade and the genuine implementation of BIM methodology, which eliminates
374 market selection mechanisms and allows organizations practicing BIM washing to compete
375 effectively with companies that have undergone a real digital transformation. However, this
376 competition will only last for a while, because, as the history of technology shows, companies
377 do not grow without real innovation.

378 **Consequences of BIM washing**

379 **Consequences at the organizational level (micro-level)**

380 The phenomenon of BIM washing has paradoxically strong consequences at the organizational
381 level. On the one hand, it can be a kind of rational shortcut to legitimacy for companies, as it
382 allows them to quickly meet the expectations of their environment (e.g., private investors,
383 public contractors, business partners), improve their image of innovation, increase their
384 chances in tenders, and reduce the risk of costly, long-term digital transformation of processes.
385 However, such a strategy may bring short-term reputational and business benefits, especially
386 when the mechanisms for verifying actual BIM practices are weak or based mainly on
387 declarations.

388 On the other hand, in the long term, BIM washing perpetuates the disconnect between the
389 presented facade and actual operational practice, which generates hidden costs. The
390 organization postpones investments in competencies, standards, data, and interoperability,
391 thereby failing to build real BIM capabilities and losing the potential to improve productivity,
392 coordination quality, or error reduction. The technological and process debt also grows,
393 because when projects that actually require working on a model arise, the company incurs
394 higher costs to catch up, experiences organizational friction, and a decline in internal trust
395 (employee cynicism about the use of BIM only on paper). As a result, a strategy that protects
396 against the risks of transformation in the short term may, in the long term, limit learning and
397 weaken the competitiveness of the organization.

398 **Consequences for the organizational field (meso-level)**

399 At the market and sector level, BIM washing acts as institutional noise that distorts signals
400 about the real digital maturity of entities. If BIM declarations do not translate into practice,
401 clients and partners lose the ability to distinguish between companies that are actually capable
402 of model-based work and those that only use the BIM label as an image tool. As a result,
403 mistrust in the supply chain grows, and contractual requirements begin to escalate towards
404 formalism (more documents, certificates, and evidence instead of checking data and processes),
405 which increases transaction costs and reduces the effectiveness of cooperation. This
406 phenomenon can lead to the mistaken attribution of implementation failures to BIM technology
407 itself (BIM does not work), when the real problem is decoupling and lack of operational
408 change. At the competition level, BIM washing flattens incentives to invest: since similar
409 legitimacy can be obtained cheaper and faster through ceremonial activities, some companies
410 limit their spending on competencies, data standards, and interoperability, which slows down
411 the actual diffusion of good practices in the industry. In addition, institutional learning is
412 distorted because organizations copy visible elements of the facade (roles, tools, slogans)
413 instead of value creation mechanisms (information models, data quality control, responsibility
414 for CDE, cross-industry coordination). In the long term, BIM washing can therefore undermine
415 the effectiveness of public policies and standardization initiatives, as the formal adoption of
416 standards does not generate the expected productivity gains, and regulatory pressure increases
417 without a parallel increase in the market's implementation capacity. The result is a perpetuating
418 cycle: greater pressure on BIM reinforces strategies of pretense, which further widens the gap
419 between the promise of digitization and its actual implementation.

420 **Implications for public policy (macro-level)**

421 Reducing BIM washing requires, above all, shifting the assessment from declarations and
422 artifacts to verifiable data work practices and process results. The most effective mechanisms
423 are those that reduce the profitability of decoupling: on the part of the contracting authorities,
424 this means precise information requirements (Employer's Information Requirements/ Asset
425 Information Requirements), clearly defined data and model quality criteria, the obligation to
426 provide access to the CDE environment with a history of decisions, and reviews based on data
427 samples (e.g., checking the structure of information, attributes, versioning, compliance with
428 the BIM Execution Plan). In contracts, it is worth strengthening evidence of use rather than
429 evidence of ownership, as this provides not only a list of tools and roles, but also traces of the
430 process (CDE logs, model coordination, clash detection protocols with links to model
431 elements). It also helps to divide requirements into maturity levels, with a realistic scope for
432 different types of projects, so that institutional pressure does not force superficial
433 implementations.

434 On the organizational side, it is crucial to complete decoupling by building operational
435 capabilities, i.e., creating information standards, assigning responsibility for data, building the
436 competence of project teams, and creating metrics that show whether BIM actually supports
437 the work (e.g., the percentage of coordination issues resolved based on the model, the quality
438 and completeness of attributes, versioning stability, response time in CDE). Equally important
439 is changing management, i.e., training related to design practice, support for leaders, and the
440 creation of conditions in which working on the model is easier than returning to emails and
441 PDFs (clear procedures, templates, automation, clear roles). To avoid a facade, the BIM
442 Manager should not be just a representative role; they must have the mandate to interfere in the
443 process, standards, and reporting methods.

444 At the industry level, limiting BIM washing enhances transparency and common rules of the
445 game. Audits and certifications that examine not so many documents as the process itself
446 (project samples, how CDE is used, data quality), as well as benchmarking initiatives and the

447 exchange of good practices between organizations, yield good results. Finally, it is important
448 to design regulations and standards in such a way that they do not reward the mere possession
449 of BIM but consistently require a minimum level of information use at key points in the project
450 (coordination, data transfer, facility maintenance). Then institutional pressure continues to
451 drive adoption, but it becomes pressure for real practice, not just for show.

452 **Conclusions**

453 This paper has shown that BIM washing can be understood as a strategy of ceremonial
454 adoption, in which organizations, under institutional pressure, build external legitimacy for the
455 use of BIM without simultaneously implementing operational changes that would deliver real
456 benefits from working with the model. The key mechanism enabling this phenomenon is
457 decoupling, i.e., the separation of the front stage (communication, roles, symbols, declarations
458 of compliance) from the back stage (actual design practices still based on 2D, PDF, and
459 traditional coordination).

460 Based on a cyclical model, it has been shown that BIM washing is not a one-off deviation, but
461 a self-perpetuating process, as isomorphic pressures lead to a transformation dilemma that
462 favors superficial choices, and entrenched decoupling reinforces imitation and normalizes
463 facade implementations. The consequences of this mechanism have both an organizational
464 dimension (short-term reputational benefits at the expense of competence debt and loss of
465 potential for efficiency improvements) and a sectoral dimension (distortion of market signals,
466 increased formalism, decline in trust, and slowdown in the real diffusion of good practices).

467 Limiting BIM washing requires shifting the evaluation criteria from declarations to evidence
468 of use, i.e., verifiable traces of the process, quality of information, CDE work practices, and
469 impact metrics. This approach reduces the profitability of decoupling, stabilizes stakeholder
470 expectations, and strengthens the conditions in which BIM becomes part of a real
471 transformation rather than just a communication label. As a result, the entire work addresses
472 the problem of BIM washing as a significant barrier to digital maturity in the construction
473 sector and justifies the need to design requirements and implementation practices in such a way
474 that they reward really organizational and informational change.

475 **Statement of Human Research Ethics Compliance**

476 This is a theoretical study and did not involve human participants.

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